

MONOFLUOARSENATES AND THEIR ANALOGY WITH SULPHATES.
BASIC MONOFLUOARSENATES OF BIVALENT METALS (Cu & Ni)

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It has been shown previously by the authors ((*Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1955, 285, 92) that the monofluoarsenate ion is analogous to sulphate ion, being isoelectronic isosters, in the salts of monovalent and bivalent metals. From the above observations, the study of the basic salts of monofluoarsenates was deemed necessary to extend the above analogies. Considering broadly, the basic salts are the results of the action of a neutral salt with the oxide or hydroxide of the corresponding metal. Numerous investigators worked on the problem of basic salts, especially of those of copper. Various studies have been made on the basic sulphates of copper. Binder (*Compt. rend.*, 1934, 198, 653) from the phase rule has obtained the basic sulphate, $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 3 \text{CuO}$. It has been supported by X-ray examination. Conductometric and potentiometric methods were used by Chretien and Heubel (*ibid.*, 1944, 219, 363) and Marie-Lousier-Breuty (*ibid.*, 1944, 219, 931) respectively to study the basic sulphate formation of copper. Both methods indicate the formation of the basic salt, $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 3 \text{CuO}$, but they fail to give any indication of the formation of the basic salt $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{CuO}$. Mitra (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 43) obtained one basic fluoberyllate of copper having the composition $\text{CuBeF}_4 \cdot 4 \text{CuO}$ and similarly for nickel. Fluoberyllate ion is quite analogous to sulphate ion and also to monofluoarsenate ion.

Attempts have been made in this laboratory to prepare the basic monofluoarsenates of copper and nickel; a few of these have been described in the present paper.

Ammonium Acetate Method.—In this method, about *M* 5 solutions of the salt and ammonium acetate were mixed in 1 : 4 proportions and left aside for several days. An insoluble precipitate appeared, which was filtered, washed with water and ethanol, and dried in the folds of filter paper.

Preparations were also tried by the method of Guy and Gire (*Compt. rend.*, 1935, 200, 1213) and of Lamure (*ibid.*, 1945, 220, 601) using magnesium powder, the function of which is to neutralise the free acid liberated and to maintain a higher pH throughout. The following salts have been prepared:

(a). $\text{CuAsO}_3\text{F} \cdot 4 \text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 8 \text{H}_2\text{O}$.—It is insoluble in water, light blue in colour and when heated to higher temperatures, it loses its water of hydration, followed by decomposition with evolution of vapour of arsenic. (Found: Cu, 42.82; As, 10.18; F, 2.64. Calc. Cu, 42.98; As, 10.14; F, 2.56%).

(b). $\text{NiAsO}_3\text{F} \cdot 4 \text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$.—Same as above. (Found: Ni, 44.36; As, 11.40; F, 2.93. Calc. Ni, 44.30; As, 11.34; F, 2.87%).

